

Obtención de un asistente conversacional basado en IA para proporcionar información específica de los medicamentos a pacientes y ciudadanía des de una perspectiva demand-driven mediante compra pública de innovación

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<p><i>Abstract (Translation from the original abstract)</i></p>	<p>Adherence to treatment in chronic diseases remains around 50%, leading to suboptimal therapeutic outcomes and reduced health system efficiency. Adherence is influenced by patient-related factors, such as medication health literacy (MHL), and health system constraints, including limited consultation time and inadequate patient information. Artificial intelligence (AI) offers opportunities to address these challenges by improving MHL. This study describes the conceptualization of an AI-based conversational assistant designed to provide real-time, understandable, and validated medication information to patients. Using a demand-driven innovation approach, clinical needs, market maturity, and system feasibility were assessed to define and prioritize solution requirements aligned with health system capabilities.</p>

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